

Chemistry of Thorium. Part II. Amino Derivatives of Thorium Tetrachloride

Sarju Prasad and Suresh Kumar

The amino derivatives of thorium (IV) chloride have been prepared by the action of ThCl_4 on some aromatic secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases. The properties of the compounds have been studied and their structures discussed.

Matthews¹ obtained $\text{ThCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ and $\text{ThCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$ by the action of ThCl_4 on pyridine and quinoline respectively in ether. He also prepared $\text{ThBr}_4 \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ by the action of ThBr_4 on the base in ether. Young² obtained $\text{ThBr}_4 \cdot 3\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ by the action of ThBr_4 on the base at the boiling temperature of the solution. The authors have prepared a number of complexes of ThCl_4 with aromatic primary mono- and diamines³. The work has now been extended to study the action of ThCl_4 on some aromatic secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases under similar conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anhydrous thorium tetrachloride was prepared by the method of Dean and Chandler³ and extracted with anhydrous ether. The chemicals used were of B.D.H. or Merck's 'extra-pure' quality.

General Procedure.—In all the cases moderately dilute ethereal solution of the base was slowly added to the ethereal solution of ThCl_4 with constant shaking till precipitation was complete. In case of methylaniline and α -picoline, due to non-separation of the compound under above conditions, ethereal solution of ThCl_4 was added with the benzene solution of the respective base. It was allowed to stand for an hour in a desiccator, filtered, and washed with ether till free of the reactants. The precipitate was dried over fused CaCl_2 in a vacuum desiccator at the room temperature and analysed by estimating thorium as ThO_2 , chlorine by Piria and Schiff's method, and nitrogen by Dumas' combustion method (Table I).

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, amorphous, and insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in HNO_3 . These compounds are fairly stable in dry atmosphere, but are hydrolysed in moist air to form generally a pasty mass; hydrolysis is more pronounced with hot or cold water or aq. alkali solution. Their stability runs in the following order: primary > secondary < tertiary, and probably they have got similar structures.

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1898, 20, 815.
2. *Ibid.*, 1934, 56, 29.
3. *This Journal*, 1961, 39, 84C.
4. *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, 1957, 2, 57.

Further, perhaps chelation brings extra stability to the compounds obtained with *p*-amino-(dimethyl and diethyl)-anilines, which are resistant to the hydrolytic action of water or aqueous alkali solution, whereas compounds with dimethyl- and diethylaniline are readily hydrolysed on exposure to open air. These compounds on being heated alone generally decompose and furnish coloured sublimes which respond to the test for: NH, N, and Cl groups, but compounds with ethylaniline and piperidine have very sharp melting points. On being heated with soda-lime respective base is liberated, condensing in the cooler parts of the tube.

TABLE I
Compounds of thorium (IV) chloride with aromatic amines (sec. & ter.) and heterocyclic bases.

Amine.	Temp.	% Thorium.		% Chlorine.		% Nitrogen.		Probable formula.
		Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
A. Secondary and tertiary amines.								
Methylaniline	..	28.38	28.94	17.23	17.70	6.59	6.98	[Th(C ₆ H ₅ NHCH ₃) ₄]Cl ₄
Ethylaniline	M.p. 140°	26.71	27.04	16.77	16.54	6.34	6.52	[Th(C ₆ H ₅ NHC ₂ H ₅) ₄]Cl ₄
Benzylaniline	Decomp. 162°	21.57	20.98	12.53	12.83	5.21	5.06	[Th(C ₆ H ₅ NHCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅) ₄]Cl ₄
Diphenylamine	.. 73°	22.60	22.10	13.09	13.52	5.17	5.33	[Th(C ₆ H ₅ NHC ₆ H ₅) ₄]Cl ₄
Dimethylaniline	.. 80°	26.58	27.04	16.87	16.54	6.19	6.52	[Th{C ₆ H ₅ N(CH ₃) ₂ } ₄]Cl ₄
Diethylaniline	.. 65°	24.28	23.92	14.35	14.63	5.54	5.77	[Th{C ₆ H ₅ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ } ₄]Cl ₄
<i>p</i> -Aminodimethylaniline	.. 125°	36.29	35.02	22.22	21.97	8.89	8.66	[Th{H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ N(CH ₃) ₂ } ₂]Cl ₄
<i>p</i> -Aminodiethylaniline	.. 77°	32.58	33.06	20.68	20.21	7.61	7.97	[Th{H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ } ₂]Cl ₄
B. Heterocyclic bases.								
α-Picoline	..	48.67	49.69	29.72	30.70	2.80	2.97	[Th(C ₅ H ₄ CH ₃ N)]Cl ₄
Piperidine	M.p. 205°	33.59	33.26	19.72	19.88	7.51	7.84	[Th(C ₅ H ₁₁ N)]Cl ₄
Piperazine	Decomp. 125°	43.01	42.50	26.42	26.00	10.01	10.25	[Th(C ₄ H ₁₀ N ₂) ₂]Cl ₄
2-Aminopyridine	.. 105°	40.73	41.29	23.59	25.26	10.26	9.96	[Th(H ₂ NC ₅ H ₄ N)]Cl ₄
Nicotine	.. 120°	32.97	33.24	20.30	20.44	8.38	8.02	[Th(C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₂) ₂]Cl ₄

The authors' sincere thanks are due to the authorities of the Banaras Hindu University for providing necessary facilities.